

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 51

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 51

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 51:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of David, when †Nathan the prophet came to him, after he had gone in to Bathsheba.</p>	<p>Psa. 51:1 לְמִנְצַחַת מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד :</p>
<p>Psa. 51:1 "Be gracious to me, O God, according to Your loving-kindness; According to the greatness of ^bYour compassion ^ablot out my transgressions. ² "Wash me thoroughly from my iniquity And ^bcleans^e me from my sin. ³ For ¹I ^aknow my transgressions, And my sin is ever before me. ⁴ "Against You, You only, I have sinned And done what is ^bevil in Your sight, So that ^aYou ¹are justified ²when You speak And ³blameless when You judge.</p>	<p>Psa. 51:2 הַנְּבִיאַ כַּאֲשֶׁר-בָּא אֶל-בֵּית-שִׁבְעָ : ³ תְּחַנְּנֵנִי אֱלֹהִים כְּחַסְדֶּךָ כְּרֹב רַחֲמֶיךָ מִחַתָּה כְּשִׁעִי : ⁴ הִרְבֵּה [הִרְבֵּה] כִּבְסִנִּי מֵעוֹנֵי וּמַחֲטָאתִי טַהַרְנֵנִי : ⁵ כִּי-כִשְׁעֵי אֲנִי אֲדַע וְחַטָּאתִי נִגְדֵי תִמְיֹד : ⁶ לֵךְ לְבִדְךָ וְחַטָּאתִי וְהָרַע בְּעֵינֶיךָ עֲשִׂיתִי לְמַעַן תִּצְדַּק בְּדַבְּרֶךָ תִּזְכֶּה בְּשִׁפְטֶיךָ : ⁷ הֵן-בְּעֵוֹן חוֹלַלְתִּי וּבְחַטָּא יַחַמְתֵּנִי אֱמִי : ⁸ הֵן-אֶמֶת חַפְצָתָ בִּשְׁחֹת וּבְסֹתָם חֲכָמָה תוֹדִיעֵנִי : ⁹ תְּחַטְּאֵנִי בְּאֵזֹב וְאֶטְהַר תְּכַבֵּסֵנִי</p>
<p>Psa. 51:5 Behold, I was ^abrought forth in iniquity, And in sin my mother conceived me. ⁶ Behold, You desire ^atruth in the ¹innermost being, And in the hidden part You will ^bmake me know wisdom. ⁷ ¹Purify me ^awith hyssop, and I shall be clean; ²Wash me, and I shall be ^bwhiter than snow.</p>	<p>בְּאֵזֹב וְאֶטְהַר תְּכַבֵּסֵנִי</p>

⁸ ¹Make me to hear ^ajoy and gladness,
Let the ^bbones which You have broken rejoice.

⁹ ^aHide Your face from my sins
And blot out all my iniquities.

Psa. 51:10 ^aCreate ^lin me a ^bclean heart, O God,
And renew ^{2a} ^asteadfast spirit within me.

¹¹ ^aDo not cast me away from Your presence
And do not take Your ^bHoly Spirit from me.

¹² Restore to me the ^ajoy of Your salvation
And sustain me with a ^bwilling spirit.

¹³ *Then* I will ^ateach transgressors Your ways,
And sinners will ^{1b} ^bconverted to You.

Psa. 51:14 Deliver me from ^abloodguiltiness, O God, ^bthe God of my salvation;

Then my ^atongue will joyfully sing of Your righteousness.

¹⁵ O Lord, ^{1a} ^aopen my lips,
That my mouth may ^bdeclare Your praise.

¹⁶ For You ^ado not delight in sacrifice, otherwise I would give it;
You are not pleased with burnt offering.

¹⁷ The sacrifices of God are a ^abroken spirit;
A broken and a contrite heart, O God, You will not despise.

וּמִשְׁלֵג אֶלְבִּין : ¹⁰ תִּשְׂמִיעֵנִי
שִׁשׁוֹן וְשִׂמְחָה תִּגְלֶנָּה עֲצָמוֹת
דְּכִיתָ : ¹¹ הַסִּתֵּר פָּנֶיךָ
מִחַטָּאֵי וְכֹל-עֲוֹנֹתַי מִחָה :
¹² לֵב טָהוֹר בְּרָא-לִי
אֱלֹהִים וְרוּחַ נְכוֹן חִדָּשׁ
בְּקִרְבִּי : ¹³ אַל-תִּשְׁלִיכֵנִי
מִלְּפָנֶיךָ וְרוּחַ קִדְשְׁךָ אַל-
תִּקַּח מִמֶּנִּי : ¹⁴ הַשִּׁיבָה לִּי
שִׁשׁוֹן יִשְׁעֶךָ וְרוּחַ נְדִיבָה
תִּסְמְכֵנִי : ¹⁵ אַל-מִדָּה
כַּשְׁעִים דְּרָכֶיךָ וְחַטָּאִים
אֵלֶיךָ יָשׁוּבוּ : ¹⁶ הַצִּילֵנִי
מִדְּמִים אֱלֹהִים אֱלֹהֵי
תִּשׁוּעָתִי תִרְגַּן לְשׁוֹנִי
צִדְקָתְךָ : ¹⁷ אֲדַנֵּי שִׁפְתֵי
תִּפְתַּח וּפִי יַגִּיד תְּהִלָּתְךָ : ¹⁸
כִּי אֵל-תַּחֲפֹץ זָבַח וְאַתָּנָה
עֹלָה לֹא תִרְצֶה : ¹⁹ זִבְחֵי
אֱלֹהִים רוּחַ נְשִׁבָרָה לֵב-
נְשִׁבָר וְנִדְכָה אֱלֹהִים לֹא
תִבְזֶה : ²⁰ הִיטִיבָה בְּרִצּוֹנְךָ
אֶת-צִיּוֹן תִּבְנֶה תוֹמֹת

Psa. 51:18 ^aBy Your favor do good to Zion;
^bBuild the walls of Jerusalem.
¹⁹ Then You will delight in
^{1a}righteous sacrifices,
 In ^bburnt offering and whole burnt offering;
 Then ²young bulls will be offered on Your altar.

יְרוּשָׁלַם׃ 21 אֲזוּ תַחֲפֹץ
 זְבַח־צֶדֶק עֹלָה וְכֹלִיל אֲזוּ
 יַעֲלוּ עַל־מִזְבְּחֶךָ פָּרִים׃

References

Psalm 51:0

†2 Sam 12:1

Psalm 51:1

^aPs 4:1; 109:26

^bPs 69:16; 106:45

^cPs 51:9; Is 43:25; 44:22; Acts 3:19; Col 2:14

Psalm 51:2

^aPs 51:7; Is 1:16; 4:4; Jer 4:14; Acts 22:16; Rev 1:5

^bJer 33:8; Ezek 36:33; Heb 9:14; 1 John 1:7, 9

Psalm 51:3

¹Or *I myself know*

^aIs 59:12

Psalm 51:4

¹Or *may be in the right*

²Many mss read *in Your words*

³Lit *pure*

^aGen 20:6; 39:9; 2 Sam 12:13; Ps 41:4

^bLuke 15:21

^cRom 3:4

Psalm 51:5

^aJob 14:4; 15:14; Ps 58:3; Eph 2:3

Psalm 51:6

¹Or *inward parts*

^aJob 38:36; Ps 15:2

^bProv 2:6; Eccl 2:26; James 1:5

Psalm 51:7

¹Or *May You purify...that I may be clean*

²Or *May You wash*

^aEx 12:22; Lev 14:4; Num 19:18; Heb 9:19

^bIs 1:18

Psalm 51:8

¹Or *May You make*
^aIs 35:10; Joel 1:16
^bPs 35:10

Psalm 51:9

^aJer 16:17

Psalm 51:10

¹Lit *for*

²Or *an upright*

^aEzek 18:31; Eph 2:10

^bPs 24:4; Matt 5:8; Acts 15:9

^cPs 78:37

Psalm 51:11

^{a2} Kin 13:23; 24:20; Jer 7:15

^bIs 63:10, 11

Psalm 51:12

^aPs 13:5

^bPs 110:3

Psalm 51:13

¹Or *turn back*

^aActs 9:21, 22

^bPs 22:27

Psalm 51:14

^{a2} Sam 12:9; Ps 26:9

^bPs 25:5

^cPs 35:28; 71:15

Psalm 51:15

¹Or *may You open*

^aEx 4:15

^bPs 9:14

Psalm 51:16

^{a1} Sam 15:22; Ps 40:6

Psalm 51:17

^aPs 34:18

Psalm 51:18

¹Or *May You build*

^aPs 69:35; Is 51:3

^bPs 102:16; 147:2

Psalm 51:19

¹Or *sacrifices of righteousness*

²Lit *they will offer young bulls*

^aPs 4:5

^bPs 66:13, 15

Targum

Psa. 51:1 For praise; a hymn of David.

Psa. 51:2 When Nathan the prophet came to him when he had lain with Bathsheba. ³ Have mercy on me, O LORD, according to your kindness; according to the abundance of your mercies, forgive my rebellion. ⁴ Cleanse me thoroughly from my iniquity, and make me clean from my sin. ⁵ For my rebellions are manifest before me, and my sin is in front of me always. ⁶ Before you, you alone, I have sinned, and that which is evil in your presence I have done; so that you may make me righteous when you speak, you will clear me when you give judgment. ⁷ Behold, in iniquity was I born, and in sin my mother was pregnant with me. [ANOTHER TARGUM: Behold, in iniquities my father thought to create me; and in the sin of the evil impulse my mother conceived me.] ⁸ Behold, you desire truth in the inner being ; and in the hidden place of the heart you will make wisdom known. ⁹ You will sprinkle me like a priest who sprinkles with hyssop waters of purification made from the ashes of the heifer on the unclean, and I will be clean; you will wash me, and I will be whiter than snow. ¹⁰ You will proclaim to me joy and jubilation; the limbs that you have purified will rejoice with a hymn. ¹¹ Remove your face from my sins, and blot out all my iniquities. ¹² A pure heart create for me, O God; and renew within me a spirit inclined to revere you. ¹³ Do not cast me from your presence; and do not remove from me your holy spirit of prophecy. ¹⁴ Return your Torah to me, to exult in your redemption; and may the spirit of prophecy support me. ¹⁵ I will teach the rebellious your ways, and sinners will return to your presence. ¹⁶ Deliver me from the sentence of death, O LORD, God of my salvation; my tongue will rejoice in your generosity. ¹⁷ O LORD, open my lips with Torah, and my mouth will recount your praise. ¹⁸ For you will not desire the holy sacrifice; when I give a burnt offering, you are not pleased. ¹⁹ The holy sacrifice of God is a broken spirit; a heart broken and purged, O God, you will not spurn. ²⁰ Show favor in your good will to Zion; you will complete the walls of Jerusalem. ²¹ Then you will desire the sacrifices of righteousness, burnt offering and holocaust; then the priests will sacrifice bulls on your altar.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

King David had committed adultery and murder because of his lust for Bathsheba. This psalm is his prayer to the LORD for forgiveness. He expresses his repentance for his mistake. Interestingly, in the Prologue of the Sefer Zohar, there is a narrative about David and Bathsheba being soul mates. It says that David had to do what he did to be with his soul mate. The child conceived from the adultress act died just as the prophet Nathan predicted. However, the second child was Solomon. It was Solomon who built the first Temple to the LORD in Jerusalem. That is part of the reasoning behind the Zohar's explanation of the event. It was a sinful event, and David repented. In the Torah, two acts required the death penalty. One was premeditated murder, while the second was adultery. King David committed both. Therefore, it is interesting that the LORD accepted David's repentance.

Superscript

David called upon the Sefirah Netzach for victory over his sins. The prophet Nathan was sent by the LORD to tell David about his sin but, more importantly, to help David repent and return to the LORD's good graces.

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory, a psalm of David.

When Nathan the prophet came to him after he had gone to Bathsheba.

Verse one

David turns to the LORD with a plea. He demonstrated his broken spirit and asked for forgiveness. David called upon the Sefirah Chesed for His loving-kindness.

Be gracious to me, O God, from the love of the Sefirah Chesed with full compassion, blot out my transgressions.

Verse two

A transgression is twofold in nature. It is a sin against one's external world and a violation of one's inner purity. David knew well that he sinned when he went to Bathsheba. Then he committed another sin to cover up the first sin. He did not make things better with the coverup. Instead, he made things a lot worse for Bathsheba and himself.

Wash me thoroughly from my sins and cleanse me from my transgression.

Verse three

David admits to his sin. He did not try to deceive himself that what he did was fine. He accepted the responsibility for his transgressions.

For my transgressions are known to me, and my sin is ever before me.

Verse four

The Sages said that David's sin with Bathsheba and his murder of Uriah were violations of the spirit rather than the letter of the legal code of the land (this can be

found in the Talmud Shabbos 56b). However, in the sight of the LORD, the crimes were grievous.

Theologians had to determine why David was forgiven for the two capital crimes. Also, the LORD did not remove David from the throne. King Saul consulted with a fortune teller before going into battle against the Philistines, which cost him and his family the throne of Israel. Then David committed two crimes far worse than King Saul's actions, and he was "forgiven." History says that Absalom, David's firstborn son, gathered men together and had an armed revolt. Because of his actions, Absalom wanted to remove his father David from the throne. The revolt did not work.

History says that Solomon took the throne after David. Solomon was the second child of David and Bathsheba. Theologians say that this is additional proof that the LORD forgave him. Was the LORD involved in this part of history, or did He sit back and watch? David was a popular king and built a mighty kingdom. Therefore, the revolt against him did not succeed. So, was it the LORD's intervention, or was the kingdom structure that David built that kept David in power?

Rabbi Steinsaltz said that even though people violate the Torah's different laws, the world continues. In light of that statement projected back to David, the thought is that the LORD did not intervene in the David Bathsheba affair. David broke the law, and life continued. Then a conclusion that follows is the LORD has not been involved with people's daily experiences.

But that goes against what Judaism and Christianity teach. Perhaps it can be said that the LORD influences events through the Sefirot and the Shekinah. Of course, the idea of free choice must be added to the equation. Then Rabbi Steinsaltz's statement about following the Torah works. Each person has the right to choose to follow the Torah. Therefore, David had the free choice to violate the Torah and have an affair with Bathsheba. It would have been up to the kingdom's people to determine if David would have to pay the penalty for his actions. If Abolom's revolt had been successful, then justice for Uriah would have occurred. But the rebellion failed, and Uriah never received justice.

King David was considered the best of the kings. His emblem, the Star of David, symbolizes the Jewish people. So, what the story of David shows is that even the most righteous person is capable of falling into the trap of sin. David saw Bathsheba nude on the top of her home. He liked what he saw and did what he had to do to have her. Even though he knew he was violating the Torah, he did it anyway.

This story is accepted by saying that David was forgiven by the LORD and rewarded. The reward was Solomon and the Temple. Even the Zohar prologue story that David had to marry Bathsheba because they were soulmates is another way to say that the LORD did not intervene. Some theologians would probably say that the death of their firstborn child was a punishment. Losing a child in childbirth is a horrific ordeal. Was that a punishment or a complication of childbirth? Probably today, that child might have been saved.

How much the LORD operates in the world will always be a question. Perhaps one day, an answer will be given to us.

Against You, and against You alone, have I sinned and done that which is evil in Your sight; therefore, You are just in Your speech and pure in Your judgment.

Verses five and six

Augustine could have used verse five to justify his original sin doctrine.

בְּעֲוֹן (b'avvon) – means “in iniquity.” Hirsch says that this word is spelled with two ׀; therefore, it means "to commit a sin." Usually, this word has only one ׀. The translation of the verse then refers to human nature to commit sin. It is a part of human nature to commit sin. It does not mean that David believed that his conception was sinful. The NASB English translation and other translations have this in their translation.

Behold I was begotten with the capacity to sin, and with a predisposition to iniquity did my mother nurse me.

Behold, however, it is also true that You have directed Your will to that which is hidden by the body and that You teach me wisdom in that which is concealed.

Verse seven

David realized how low he had sunk morally and ethically. He understood the dual nature of humanity. One part is the spark of the LORD, the Neshamah, and the other is the physical body that is a part of the soul. The LORD's purity vs. the flesh's desires is always in conflict. In this situation, David allowed the wishes of his flesh to overwhelm his soul. This problem has plagued humankind from the beginning of the species' existence. The dual nature is introduced in Genesis with Adam and Chava disobeying the LORD and continues throughout history. David prays that the LORD would cleanse him of the sin of his flesh.

Therefore, cleanse me with hyssop so I may be clean; wash me, and I can still become whiter than snow.

Verse eight

David offers his plea to the LORD to regain his physical and spiritual purity. He hoped that he would rise again and have a renewed strength.

Make me hear joy and gladness, let the bones which you have broken rejoice.

Verse nine

David asks the LORD to rebuild their relationship, asking the LORD to forget about his past sins.

Do not view my sins and erase your knowledge of them.

Verse ten

The difference between humans and the rest of the animal kingdom is that humans can make free choices and know what is right or wrong. Humans can use their intellect to control their physical urges and desires. David lost that ability when he took Bathsheba. He asked the LORD to restore him. He used the metaphor of the heart to speak about his spiritual well-being.

Create for me a clean heart, O God, and renew a steadfast spirit within me.

Verse eleven

David was selected by the LORD as a messenger and servant of His work to the Jewish people and the world. David prays that the LORD would not dispose of him like a used tool.

Do not cast me from your presence, and do not take away your Shekinah from me.

Verse twelve

David asked the LORD to help him to rise again to the spiritual purity he had before the incident.

Restore in me the joy of Your salvation, and let the spirit of free devotion uphold me.

Verse thirteen

David said he would teach the people about the LORD's kindness and that sinners can be restored to favor.

Then I will teach sinners Your ways, and men have grown old in sin how they may return to You.

Verse fourteen

The blood guilt is for the two sins David committed that required death. The LORD forgave David. He did not have to die for these sins.

Deliver me from the guilt of blood, O God, God of my victory, so that my tongue may rejoice in the justice of Your loving-kindness.

Verse fifteen

David prayed to reenter the LORD's love.

O LORD, open my lips that my mouth may declare Your praise.

Verse sixteen

Kings did not bring offerings to the LORD.

For You do not demand that I bring sacrifices, and You do not desire burnt offerings.

Verse seventeen

A true offering to the LORD is a spirit broken by the awareness of sin committed.

The sacrifice to God is a broken spirit and a contrite heart, O God, you will not despise.

Verses eighteen and nineteen

There are offerings made to the LORD because of the sins of humans. They serve as a means to help the worshiper in his/her efforts to regain a high moral level and favor with the LORD.

By Your favor, do good to Zion; build the walls of Jerusalem.

Then You will delight in righteous sacrifices, in burnt offerings and whole burnt offerings, then young bulls will be offered on Your altar.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory, a psalm of David.

When Nathan the prophet came to him after he had gone to Bathsheba.

Be gracious to me, O God, from the love of the Sefirah Chesed with full compassion, blot out my transgressions.

Wash me thoroughly from my sins and cleanse me from my transgression.

For my transgressions are known to me, and my sin is ever before me.

Against You, and against You alone, have I sinned and done that which is evil in Your sight; therefore, You are just in Your speech and pure in Your judgment.

Behold I was begotten with the capacity to sin, and with a predisposition to iniquity did my mother nurse me.

Behold, however, it is also true that You have directed Your will to that which is hidden by the body and that You teach me wisdom in that which is concealed.

Therefore, cleanse me with hyssop so I may be clean; wash me, and I can still become whiter than snow.

Make me hear joy and gladness, let the bones which you have broken rejoice.

Do not view my sins and erase your knowledge of them.

Create for me a clean heart, O God, and renew a steadfast spirit within me.

Do not cast me from your presence, and do not take away your Shekinah from me.

Restore in me the joy of Your salvation, and let the spirit of free devotion uphold me.

Then I will teach sinners Your ways, and men have grown old in sin how they may return to You.

Deliver me from the guilt of blood, O God, God of my victory, so that my tongue may rejoice in the justice of Your loving-kindness.

O LORD, open my lips that my mouth may declare Your praise.

For You do not demand that I bring sacrifices, and You do not desire burnt offerings.

The sacrifice to God is a broken spirit and a contrite heart, O God, you will not despise.

By Your favor, do good to Zion; build the walls of Jerusalem.

Then You will delight in righteous sacrifices, in burnt offerings and whole burnt offerings, then young bulls will be offered on Your altar.

Appendix

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Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

